

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL RESEARCH

MODELING OF DRUG DELIVERY THROUGH THIN LAYER POLYMERIC FILMS IN DOSAGE FORM TECHNOLOGIES: RECENT DEVELOPMENTS AND FUTURE CHALLENGES

N. Sumiya*, K. Vanaja, A. Deevan Paul, Chitra Prasanthi, K. Thyagaraju, A. Murali Krishna

SVU College of Pharmaceutical Sciences, SV Univeristy, Tirupati.

ARTICLE INFO

Article history

Received 13/09/2018

Available online

31/10/2018

Keywords

Orodispersible Films,
Mucoadhesive
Properties,
Bio-Availability,
Polymeric Matrices.

ABSTRACT

Orodispersible films have been identified as an alternative approach to conventional dosage forms. The films are considered to be convenient to swallow, self-administrable, and fast dissolving dosage form, out of that it has a versatile platform for drug delivery. This delivery system has been used for both systemic and local action through several routes such as oral, buccal, sublingual, ocular, and transdermal routes. The sublingual and buccal delivery of a drug through thin film has the potential to improve the onset of action, lower the dosing, and enhance the efficacy and safety profile of the medicament. The films are polymeric matrices designed to be mucoadhesive properties and usually formulated with permeability enhancers to improve bioavailability. Among all fast release dosage forms, orodispersible films are successful to attract pharmaceutical industry due to ease of formulation and extension patent life. Films are popular in patients too because of quick onset and user-friendliness of the dosage form. Films rapidly hydrate and then disintegrate and/or dissolve to release the medication. This article provides a framework for further discussion and scientific work to improve orodispersible films.

Corresponding author

N. Sumiya

M.Pharmacy Second year

Department of Pharmaceutics

SVU College of Pharmaceutical Sciences,

SV Univeristy, Tirupati- 517502

sumiyasummus@gmail.com

Please cite this article in press as **K. Vanaja et al. Modeling of Drug Delivery Through Thin Layer Polymeric Films In Dosage Form Technologies: Recent Developments And Future Challenges. Indo American Journal of Pharmaceutical Research.2018:8(10).**

Copy right © 2018 This is an Open Access article distributed under the terms of the Indo American journal of Pharmaceutical Research, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

INTRODUCTION

Oral films are the most advanced form of oral solid dosage form due to more flexibility and comfort. It improves the efficacy of APIs by dissolving within a minute in the oral cavity after the contact with saliva without chewing and no need of water for administration. It gives quick absorption and instant bioavailability of drugs due to high blood flow and permeability of oral mucosa is 4-1000 times greater than that of skin. FDOFs are useful in patients such as pediatrics, geriatrics, bedridden emetic patients, diarrhoea, sudden episode of allergic attacks, for those who have an active lifestyle. It is also useful whether local action desired such as local anesthetic for toothaches, oral ulcers, teething. The oral route is the most preferred route of administration for drug delivery as it bears various advantages over another route of administration. The lower bioavailability, long onset time and dysphagia patients turned the manufacturer into the parenteral and liquid orals¹⁻².

**Fig no.1: (a) Drug delivery through the transdermal route.
(b) Drug delivery through ocular route.
(c) Drug delivery through buccal route.**

Each pharmaceutical company wants to formulate the novel oral dosage form which has the higher bioavailability, quick action, and most patient compliance so they formulate the fast dissolving tablets by using super disintegrants and hydrophilic ingredients³. Fast-dissolving drug-delivery systems were developed as an alternative to conventional dosage forms for pediatric and geriatric patients. As mentioned in Fig no. 1 a, b, c the film is prepared using hydrophilic polymers that rapidly dissolve on the tongue or buccal cavity, delivering the drug to the systemic circulation via dissolution when contact with the liquid is made. Fast dissolving oral film has emerged as an advanced alternative to the traditional tablets, capsules, and liquids often associated with prescription and OTC medications. Similar in size, shape, and thickness to a postage stamp thin-film strips are typically designed for oral administration, with the user placing the strip on or under the tongue (sublingual) or along the inside of the cheek (buccal). These drug delivery options allow the medication to bypass the first pass metabolism thereby making the medication more bioavailable. As the oral thin film dissolves, the drug can enter the bloodstream through enteric, buccal or sublingually⁴.

IDEAL CHARACTERISTICS OF A DRUG TO BE SELECTED:

- ❖ The drug should have a pleasant taste.
- ❖ The drug should have small or moderate molecular weight.
- ❖ The drug should have good stability and solubility in water and also in saliva.
- ❖ It should be partially unionized at the pH of the oral cavity.
- ❖ It should have an ability to permeate oral mucosa.
- ❖ It should be less friable and have good mechanical strength.
- ❖ It should be compatible with the other ingredients⁵⁻⁶.

ADVANTAGES:

- Availability of larger surface area that leads to rapid disintegrating and dissolution in the oral cavity.
- No need for water, drug wet by saliva and instantly dissolves or disintegrates.
- The oral or buccal mucosa being highly vascularized, drugs can be absorbed directly and can enter the systemic circulation without undergoing first-pass hepatic metabolism.
- Patients suffering from dysphagia, repeated emesis, motion sickness, and mental disorders prefer this dosage form as they are unable to swallow a large quantity of water.
- The site-specific and rapid onset of action.
- The destructive acidic environment of the stomach can be avoided.
- Accuracy in the administered dose is assured from every strip or film.
- Pre-gastric absorption can result in improved bioavailability and as a result of reduced dosage; improved clinical performance through a reduction of unwanted effects⁷.

DISADVANTAGES:

- The main disadvantage of this delivery system is we cannot incorporate high dose into strip or film.
- Special packaging –OFDFs are fragile and must be protected from water so it needs special packaging.
- Not suitable for drugs which irritate and are unstable at buccal pH.
- Hygroscopic in nature. So, longer preservation is difficult.
- Drugs which are absorbed only by passive diffusion can be administered by this route⁸.

LIMITATIONS:

- Drugs with larger doses are difficult to formulate into FDT e.g. Rifampin (600 mg), Ethambutol (100mg) etc.
- Most bitter drugs should be avoided or taste masking is required.
- Proteinaceous drugs should be avoided if used then co-administration because of enzyme inhibitors such as Aprotinin and bestatin.
- Puromycin, bile salts required for the inhibition of proteolytic enzymes present in saliva⁹.

BUCCAL THIN FLIMS:

The buccal mucosa is an preferred route of administration for drug delivery due to its many advantages such as excellent blood supply, ease of access and administration without the need of additional devices, avoidance of the hepatic (and GIT) first-pass metabolism, and a favourable permeability profile superior to skin and similar to the floor of the mouth. Buccal administration can be addressed using different dosage forms such as patches, gels, tablets, films, and sprays that are designed to elicit either a local or systemic effect according to the therapy. In the oral cavity, three types of mucosa can be identified, namely masticatory, specialized, and lining mucosa. The masticatory mucosa is located in the hard palate and tooth gingiva and has a keratinized epithelium attached to underlying tissues by collagenous connective tissue. This structure brings resistance to abrasion and shearing forces of the masticatory process. The specialized mucosa covers the dorsal surface of the tongue and comprises regions of semi keratinized and non-keratinized epithelia. Finally, the lining mucosa is a non-keratinized tissue and covers all other oral regions providing protection and is associated with elastic deformation, facilitation of speech, and mastication¹⁰⁻¹¹.

In the oral cavity, at least three routes for administration can be identified: sublingual delivery (through the back of the tongue and the floor of the mouth), buccal delivery (through the buccal mucosa), and local delivery (within the oral cavity for a local effect). The buccal mucosa is composed of an external layer of stratified squamous epithelium comprising differentiated layers of keratinocytes changing in size, shape, and content as they progress from the basal lamina to superficial layers. Underneath the stratified epithelium, the basal lamina is followed by the lamina propria and the innermost layer is the submucosa. The skin presents a keratinized epithelium that offers better barrier properties in comparison with the gingiva and palate, also keratinized, due to a greater total lipid, non-polar lipid, ceramides and glycosylceramide content. As mentioned in Fig no.2, the non-keratinized epithelium provides protection, principally due to the relative amounts of glycosylceramides, which is not present in the keratinized epithelia. In porcine tissue, the less permeable buccal mucosa contains proportionately more glycosylceramides (18.4 mg/g) than the floor of the mouth (7.5 mg/g). The glycosylceramides content provides fluidity to the epithelium, limiting the drug absorption process. Porcine buccal and sublingual non-keratinized epithelium exhibits high quantities of the more polar phospholipids, cholesterol esters, glycosylceramides, and minimal amounts of ceramides¹²⁻¹³.

Fig no. 2: Physiology of buccal mucosa.

BENEFICIAL FEATURES OVER THE THIN FILM TECHNOLOGY TOWARDS MARKETING AND CLINICAL TRIALS:

The design of an oral formulation is generally based on two critical factors, drug therapy, and the target population. However, the choice of the type of pharmaceutical dosage form may become very difficult when specific target groups include very young children, from birth to 8 - 10 years of age, and the geriatric population. Regarding the pediatric segment, the major challenge involves the development of a specific type of dosage form suitable for children of all ages. Additionally, for both population groups, the size of the dosage form can also be a challenge, essentially due to swallowing issues. The swallowing process involves synchronized actions of several nerves and muscles. It is assumed that a safe swallowing is an ability developed since the 12 years-old. Generally, the swallowing function underlay an aging process, then, some malfunctions may be age-related, normally called as presbyphagia, but also may be due to pathological conditions, usually referred to as dysphagia. These conditions are directly related with patients' drug therapy adherence which had led to the huge concern in the development of patient-centered formulations. Therefore, liquid or orally disintegrating dosage forms have been the most preferred and exploited for these population segments. Hence, the oral films appeared as a suitable alternative to patients with swallowing difficulties and also as a more suitable and convenient dosage form when compared to the conventional oral dosage forms¹⁴⁻¹⁵.

MANUFACTURING PROCESSES OVERCOMING THE INNOVATIVE MARKETING ADVANTAGES:

From the market perspective new drug delivery technologies offer the opportunity to extend revenue life cycles for pharmaceutical companies whose drug patent is about to expire and will soon be vulnerable to generic competition. Moreover, the grant of marketing exclusivity to the new dosage form would help to enlarge the revenue. This type of formulation may also be designed to discourage common methods of tampering associated with misuse and abuse of some prescription drugs. Considering oral films as a novel dosage form for drugs already in the market, with a different pharmacokinetic profile, the approval process should be a New Drug Application (NDA) for FDA approval, or an Abridged Application, Directive 2001/83/EC, for European Marketing Authorization approval. In this case, especially for the USA market clinical studies would be essential for the FDA granting three marketing exclusivity (3-5 years)¹⁶.

CLINICAL ADVANTAGES OF THE BUCCAL FILM DOSAGE FORMS:

From the clinical point of view, some oral films may improve the oral bioavailability of drugs with extensive first-pass metabolism, by promoting the absorption of the drug substance through the oral mucosa reducing the dose necessary to achieve the therapeutic action, which may contribute also to a reduction of the side effects. Nevertheless, this absorption route may also be advantageous in drug therapies where a fast onset action is essential¹⁷.

ROUTES OF DRUG ADMINISTRATION THROUGH THIN FILM HYDRATING TECHNOLOGY:**Oral route:**

Developing polymeric films has made it possible to improve the drug bioavailability and patient adherence to drug therapy via the oral route, especially buccal and sublingual route. The anatomical and physiological characteristics of buccal mucosae, such as the existence of smooth muscles with high vascular perfusion, easy accessibility, and bypassing of first pass metabolism make it a favorable route for the drug delivery. In Fig no.3 Comparison with the other mucosa, the buccal and sublingual routes are preferable because it provides better permeability of the drug. Similarly, the oral mucosa was found to be 4–4000 times more permeable to a hydrophilic drug than the skin. The sublingual route is targeted for the delivery of drug exhibiting high permeability across the mucosa and is utilized for the treatment of acute disorders.

Fig no.3: Drug penetration into the oral mucosa to reach the Systemic circulation by using oral route film.

On the other hand, the buccal route is preferred for the treatment of chronic disease, when an extended release of the drug is desired. For achieving a promising therapeutic effect, the drug must be released from the formulation to the delivery site (e.g. sublingual or buccal region) and should penetrate the oral mucosa to reach the systemic circulation. The existence of several environmental related factors such as fluid volume, pH, enzyme activity and the permeability of oral mucosa determines the fate of drug absorption in the oral mucosa. On the other side, the amount of secretion of saliva impedes the residence of the drug at the delivery site due to washing out of the drug. While developing the oral formulation like polymeric films, all the point should be taken into account for obtaining higher therapeutic bioavailability as well as the patient adherence to the dosage form¹⁸⁻¹⁹.

Ocular route:

More than 90% of the marketed ocular formulations are in the form of solutions or suspension; however, this conventional dosage form lacks in achieving promising therapeutic success. The frequent instillation of eye drops is needed to elicit a therapeutic response. This usually leads to patient noncompliance and pulsed administration. Furthermore, the topically applied drugs to the eye generally enter the systemic circulation via the nasolacrimal duct system, which possibly causes side effects and systemic toxicity as well. With the aim of enhancing the ocular bioavailability and overcoming the ocular drug delivery barriers, the development of ophthalmic film becomes popular these days. The ophthalmic films result in the reduction of dose frequency, less systemic side effects and better therapeutic outcomes.

Fig no.4: Drug penetrate into systemic circulation By using ocular films.

Therefore, ophthalmic films could open exciting opportunities as a delivery platform of therapeutics to replace the traditional dosage forms for achieving high therapeutic success and patient adherence in Fig no.4. The flow of tear across the outer surface of the cornea is continuous, which impedes the drug diffusion leading to low bioavailability (1–7%) of drugs. Generally, the drug with higher lipophilicity encounters many problems as it cannot be dissolved in the aqueous medium of the eye. Since the drug causes discomfort in the eye, it induces blinking, and therefore causing washing out of the significant amount of drug. Therefore, the success of the effective development of films to be delivered to the eye relies on the comprehensive knowledge of the drug, the constraints to ocular drug delivery, and the excipients used. Hence, all these factors should be considered during the formulation of ocular films²⁰⁻²¹.

Transdermal route:

Drug-loaded transdermal films are the alternative to replace the existing transdermal dosage form. Numerous sustained or controlled delivery systems have been devised, where a drug is either dissolved or dispersed in the films as represented in Fig no.5 (a). The film forming system has been practiced for the transdermal delivery of steroidal hormones, analgesics, local anesthesia and antiemetic for systemic effects. Only a small number of drugs are being designed for the transdermal delivery of films as several factors affect the bioavailability of drugs such as molecular size, polarity, pH of the drug, state of the skin hydration, subcutaneous reservoir of drug and drug metabolism by skin flora as mentioned in Fig no.5(b). Similarly, the hydration of skin is crucial for increasing drug absorption, which is possible by using humectant in the film formulation.

(a) Transdermal Patch

(b) Occlusive film

Fig no.5: Transdermal films induced for the controlled and Sustained drug delivery by the occlusive patches.

The physiological factors such as regional skin site, nature of stratum corneum, the thickness of skin, and density of appendages also influence the overall outcome of the therapeutic effects of the drug. The thin film may possess better therapeutic efficacy and patient acceptance compared to the common transdermal dosage forms such as patches or gels. Due to occlusive properties of transdermal patches, it prevents the permeation of water vapor from the skin surface and causes severe pain at the time of peeling. However, polymeric thin films could be a highly promising alternative for transdermal drug delivery because of the ease of application, flexibility and better cosmetic appearance²²⁻²³

MECHANISM OF ACTION:**PHYSIOLOGY ON SKIN TOWARDS DRUG ABSORPTION:**

Skin is considered to be the largest organ of the human body with an average surface area of 1.6–2 m² and accounts for about 15% of the total body weight of an adult human. It is the outer covering of the body and has multiple layers (2-3 mm thick) which protect underlying muscles, bones, ligaments, and internal organs. It is an interface with the environment and protects the body against pathogens, controls water loss, regulates the body temperature, enables sensation to be perceived and plays a key role in the synthesis of vitamin D. It also acts as a water-resistant barrier, to protect essential nutrients in the body, and absorbs oxygen required for the outermost layer of cells as represented in Fig no.6. It is composed of mainly three layers. (1) Epidermis, (2) Dermis, (3) Hypodermis

Epidermis:

The epidermis is the thin, tough outer covering of the skin that is devoid of blood vessels, and relies on the underlying dermis for nutrition and blood supply. It is composed of several layers: Stratum germinativum: An inner cellular layer that forms new skin cells. This layer is mainly composed of keratin, which gives it strength and toughness. This basal layer also has melanocytes, which give skin its brown pigmentation to protect against ultraviolet radiation. After new cells are formed they migrate upwards to the stratum corneum and flatten at that level. Stratum corneum is composed mainly of the dead, keratinized cells. The entire epidermal layer is replaced every four weeks. In fact, it is estimated that an individual will shed about one pound of skin every year. The epidermis is innervated with sensory nerves. These nerves sense and transmit heat, pain, and other sensations.

Dermis:

The dermis, or the inner supportive layer of the skin, is made mostly of collagen and is well supplied with blood. The body's nerves, sensory receptors, blood vessels, and lymphatics are located within the dermis. The dermis also houses some epidermal derivatives such as the skin, hair, and nails.

Subcutaneous tissue:

The hypodermis, also known as the subcutaneous tissue, is mainly fat tissue that cushions the skin from injury. It aids with temperature control and provides fat for energy utilization when needed²⁴⁻²⁵.

Fig no.6: Structure of human skin corresponding to the inner cellular layer.

ABSORPTION OF DRUG THROUGH MOLECULAR DIFFUSION:

Most small-molecule drugs reach blood circulation by absorption through the intestinal epithelium, using either of the following mechanisms: passive paracellular diffusion, passive transcellular diffusion, facilitated transcellular diffusion, and transporter-mediated active transport. For biologics, not all the mentioned mechanisms are available. The physicochemical properties of the permeating molecule will determine the mechanism for absorption, and the molecular weight is one of the most important physicochemical factors. For instance, when administered orally, hydrophilic molecules with molecular weight below 200 Da are mainly absorbed by the paracellular route through the small intestinal mucosa, 500–700 Da molecules can be slightly transported by passive diffusion through small intestinal epithelial cells and are mainly transported via active transport, and larger weights over 700 Da (most biologics) permeate mainly through active transport. Paracellular transport in the intestine is restricted by claudins forming tight junction-associated pores. Transcellular transport consists of the internalization of drugs into epithelial cells followed by a release on the basolateral membrane. Moreover, bile acids and salts are conventionally used to promote the permeability and emulsify lipophilic molecules resulting in an enhanced oral bioavailability²⁶⁻²⁷.

FIRST PASS METABOLISM AVOIDING GASTRIC DRUG DEGRADATION

The first-pass effect, also known as first-pass metabolism or pre-systemic metabolism, takes place when a drug is metabolized between its site of administration and the site of sampling for drug concentration determination. This phenomenon affects both small molecules and biologics alike. The first-pass effect results in a net drug amount reduction prior to reaching systemic circulation. Proteins and peptides can be affected by hepatic first-pass metabolism, e.g., 43% of insulin has been found to be removed from the liver when administered by portal infusion. The intestine also contributes to the first-pass metabolism, and for some drugs, its effect is more important than hepatic and gastric metabolism. For instance, it has been reported that the intestine contribution to amitriptyline first pass effect has been observed in a rat model, observing 9% and 87% of hepatic and intestinal first-pass effect respectively, after an oral dose. Avoiding the first-pass effect has become a goal in pharmaceutical innovation, replacing the traditional oral route for alternative delivery routes including the buccal epithelium²⁸⁻²⁹.

PROMOTING TECHNOLOGY USING BUCCAL ADMINISTRATION:

Films are promising dosage forms for buccal administration essentially for their simplicity of administration, versatility reaching either local or systemic effect, mucoadhesion providing enough time for absorption, and small size and flexibility improving patient compliance. The FDA identifies three different types of films related to pharmaceutical drug products:

- Film: a thin layer or coating. – The film, extended release: a drug delivery system in the form of a film that releases the drug over an extended period in such a way as to maintain constant drug levels in blood or target tissue.
- Film, soluble: a thin layer or coating which is susceptible to being dissolved when in contact with the liquid. These are also known as orodispersible films, and other terms.

Mucoadhesive preparations are intended to be retained in the oral cavity by adhesion to the mucosal epithelium allowing systemic drug absorption. Films are very thin polymeric matrices intended to either be placed on the tongue, buccal, or sublingual mucosa, after which saliva hydrates and promotes dispersion/dissolution or swelling and adherence to the administration site. Depending on the formulation and intended effect, the drug will be released for either a local effect, gastrointestinal transit, or transmucosal absorption. Films can also be designed as mono or multilayer systems to further control or modify drug release. These dosage forms offer advantages to elderly people and children as they do not have to be swallowed for drug administration as opposed to tablets and capsules. Furthermore, mucoadhesive films can allow for prolonged contact times with the epithelium resulting in higher bioavailability compared to solutions and suspensions. The limitations of films as buccal dosage forms can be identified in their potential hygroscopicity, a rather small maximum dose (thus highly potent drugs will be preferred), and the need to consider sensorial requirements such as taste and texture. Currently, there are a number of pharmaceutical drug products formulated in films as dosage forms. Although validated for small-molecule drugs, no biologic drug product has been commercialized in films. Nonetheless, the pharmaceutical industry is making efforts in moving forward this strategy reflected in one pharmaceutical film product³⁰⁻³¹.

PROTEIN METABOLISM DURING PHARMACOLOGICAL ACTIVITY:

Proteins and peptides are naturally occurring molecules associated with specific functions related to homeostasis and life maintenance, but in the last decades, these large molecules have become an important focus for drug development that started growing rapidly after the introduction of the first recombinant peptide: human insulin approved by the US Food and Drug Administration (FDA) in 1982. These molecules perform important cellular functions directly correlated with their physicochemical properties such as hydrophilicity/hydrophobicity, net charge, sequence length, and periodic variation in hydrophobic residues along the chain. In general terms, the FDA classifies proteins and peptides for human use in four groups according to their pharmacological effect:

Group I: protein therapeutics with enzymatic or regulatory activity (replacing a protein that is deficient or abnormal, augmenting an existing pathway, or providing a novel function or activity)

1. Group II: protein therapeutics with special targeting activity (interfering with a molecule or organism, delivering other compounds or proteins)

2. Group III: protein vaccines (protecting against a deleterious agent, treating an autoimmune disease, or treating cancer) Group IV protein diagnostics

Every year, new proteins and especially peptides are introduced to the market due to their potency, lower toxicity compared to small molecules, and high specificity and sensibility, becoming the drug of choice for treating many diseases. Biologic products comprise proteins, peptides, sugars, nucleic acids, and their combinations. In recent years, some pharmaceutical companies have changed their focus from small molecules to biologics, which is reflected in the number of patent applications and conceded patents in this emerging field³²⁻³³.

CLINICAL POSSIBILITIES FOR THE APPLICATION TO PEDIATRICS:

Drugs are administered orally to children not only in the outpatient setting but also in the hospital. Here, a substantial proportion of drugs is administered orally even to children admitted to neonatal and pediatric intensive care units. The use of oral drugs, as opposed to intravenously administered drugs, has the advantage of less risk of adverse effects including infection, fewer costs, and easier administration without the need for an inconvenient intravenous access. In infants and neonates, a liquid formulation is the most widely used oral dosage form because of the advantage of dose flexibility combined with a lower risk of choking, as opposed to solid oral dosage forms. For these children, the use of a drug formulation, which combines an easy administration, dose flexibility with low volume fluid intake might be beneficial. As such, the use of hydrochlorothiazide in an ODF might be an important improvement in drug formulation. ODFs are easy to administer and need almost no intake of water. Once administered, an ODF sticks to the tongue or palatal and cannot spit out thereby improving patient compliance. Different ODF formulations have already been developed which are suitable as a starting point for further research. In other clinical conditions where volume restriction is important, ODFs may gain in place in the therapeutic arsenal. Many cardiovascular drugs are administered to patients in which the fluid balance is rigidly monitored and carefully balanced, because of a comprised cardiac output³⁴⁻³⁵.

PROBLEMS FOUND DURING DEVELOPMENT AND SCALE

UP OF FILM:

Die swell phenomenon:

The cross-section of the film increases upon leaving the die depending upon the viscoelastic property of polymers. So, the final dimension of the film changes due to this 'Die swell phenomenon'. The mechanism behind the phenomenon is that polymer is exposed to high shear force and high energy kneading during extrusion. So, polymer comes in a state of stress and after completion of the extrusion process, polymer tries to come into relaxation state by increasing their radius of gyration. So, the dimension of the final formulation is slightly changed. This problem can be eliminated by slow speed screw operation with slow kneading as well as gentle mixing for a long time rather than high shear kneading for short duration.

Fisheye formation:

Sometimes due to flavors or residual moisture in ingredients e.g. natural or phytochemicals products, the blend has an inherent tendency to agglomerate. Agglomerate type of uneven, irregular and non-uniform formation in the blend is called 'Fisheye'. Once 'fish eye' or agglomerations are formed, they are extremely difficult to eliminate from the blend. It will create an uneven pulsatile flow as well as uneven temperature distribution in the barrel. To eliminate 'Fisheye' formation in the blend, high shear mixing must be employed from the beginning. Incorporation of silica derivative may also avoid fish eye formation. e.g. calcium silicate to avoid fish eyes in tobacco containing blend.

Incorporation of liquids with powder blend:

In some cases, liquid ingredients (e.g. plasticizers like PEG, PG, and glycerin) are required for the smooth extrusion process. The first method of incorporating liquid into polymer blend is granulation. Granulation of piroxicam, maltodextrins and MCC blend with glycerol. Granulation of PEO with PEG 400 to improve the flow. Granulation method can provide uniform mixing and improved flow property but it will create multistep processing which is considered uneconomical from the industrial aspect. The second method is side stuffing. After molten mass formation inside the barrel, the liquid is incorporated via side stuffing port. Direct incorporation of PEG 400 into the barrel after melting of solid components in the compression zone.

Weight variation within film sheets:

Sometimes uneven films are formed due to improper flow of powder blend through the hopper. So to improve the flow property of power blend, either granulation method as discussed in section 4.3 or force feeder can be employed. In some cases, glidants are added in dry mix blend. The addition of 35% silicates to promote the flow of tobacco blends containing high moisture content phytochemicals. If weight variation is due to the uneven pulsatile flow of molten mass, gear pump provision should be provided near to end of the barrel.

Chemical stability of active during hot-melt extrusion:

During hot melt extrusion process, many chemical reactions like hydrolysis and solvolysis due to residual moisture and solvents as well as free radicals generation are initiated at elevated temperature. To solve the issue of residual moisture and solvent, preheated excipients are sometimes used in the process. To eliminate the generation of peroxides and free radicals, antioxidants like vitamin E, TPGS, butylated hydroxytoluene, and butylated hydroxyanisole are generally added to blend.

Recrystallization and nucleation of drug molecules:

At elevated temperature, pressure and intense mixing solubility of active in polymer blend are increases but recrystallization of the active molecule from the molten blend occurs after temperature drop. This problem can be prevented by preparing highly viscous molten polymer plasticizer medium³⁶⁻³⁷.

Table no: 1 Main problem related to the modification of commercially Available oral dosage forms and a good alternative.

Table no: 2 Polymers available for preparation of films:

S.NO	POLYMERS	EXAMPLES
1	Natural polymers	Pullulan,, starch, gelatin, pectin, sodium alginate, maltodextrins, polymerized rosin.
2	Synthetic polymers	Hydroxyl propyl methyl cellulose, sodium carboxymethyl cellulose, polyethylene oxide, hydroxyl propyl cellulose, polyvinyl pyrrolidone, polyvinyl alcohol.

Table no.3: Properties and key findings of representative polymers used for Preparation of thin film formulations:

POLYMERS	PROPERTIES	KEY FINDINGS
Hydroxypropyl methylcellulose (HPMC)	White, creamy, odorless, tasteless powder Molecular weight :-10,000-1,500,000 Viscosity 3-100,000 mpa-s Moderate mucoadhesive properties	Film forming ability at 2-20% concentrations Generally used for the controlled and delayed release of drug substance
Carboxymethyl cellulose (CMC)	White, odourless powder MW-90,000-700,000 Viscosity 5,13,000 mpa-s High swelling properties Good bioadhesive strength	Improved the residence time of HPC and sodium alginate films Good compatible with starch forming single phase polymeric matrix films with improved mechanical and barrier properties
Hydroxyl propyl cellulose (HPC)	White to slightly yellow colored, odorless, inert and tasteless powder MW-50,000-1,250,000 Viscosity 75-6500mpas Moderate mucoadhesive properties	Used to replace HPMC in a polymer matrix with modified starch to improve solubility
Polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVP)	A wide range of solubility Non-ionic High swelling properties Used as co-adjutant to increase mucoadhesion	The blending of PVP and PVA and HPMC improves the film forming ability As film forming, polymer exhibited non-fiction release of ketorolac and progesterone
Polyethylene oxide (PEO)	Non-ionic polymer High mucoadhesion with high molecular weight	Optimization of tear resistance, dissolution rate Tendencies of the film by combining low Mw PEO, with a higher Mw PEO and /or with cellulose. Pleasant mouth feeling with no sticky or highly viscous gel formation. Films with good resistance to tearing, minimal or no curling.
Pullulan	White, odorless and tasteless powder with a mucilaginous taste MW-8000-2,000,000 Viscosity 100-180 mm	Pullulan –HPMC films have improved thermal and mechanical properties A stable film with less permeability to oxygen
Chitosan	White or creamy powder or flakes, and odorless Biocompatible and biodegradable Obtained after deacetylation of chitin	Chitosan enhances the transport of polar drugs across epithelial surfaces Possesses cell-binding activity due to polymer cationic polyelectrolyte structure that binds to the negative charge of the cell surface
Sodium alginate	Occurs as a white or buff powder, which is odorless and tasteless Viscosity 20-400cps	Used as immobilization matrices for cells and enzymes, controlled release of bioactive substances

Carrageenan	Anionic with high mucoadhesive properties Safe, biodegradable, non-allergenic Rapid swelling and dissolution in water Purified carbohydrate product extracted from brown seaweed by the use of dilute alkali	Excellent gel and film-forming properties Compatible with most water-soluble thickeners and resins
	An anionic polysaccharide, extracted from the red seaweed <i>Chondrus crispus</i> Moderate mucoadhesive properties	Potential to act as protein/peptide stabilizer by steric stabilization It is compatible with most non-ionic and anionic water-soluble thickeners Solutions are susceptible to shear and heat degradation

IMPROVE POLYMERIC MUCOADHESIVE INNER PROPERTY:

Although the mucoadhesion concept appeared early during the eighties, it was only ten years later that improved mucoadhesive polymers were introduced in the pharmaceutical field. There are several theories that may explain the bio-adhesion process, but none is able to explain the overall mechanism. The wetting theory is one of the oldest theories and involves notions of thermodynamic work and contact angle. Briefly, the bio-adhesion in this theory is defined as the surface tension of the two adherent phases subtracted by their apparent interfacial tensions. On the other hand, the diffusion theory is related to the possible relation between the polymeric chains with the glycoprotein mucin chains. According to this theory depending on the depth of the contact, semi-permanent bonds, between the substrate and polymer adhesive chains, may occur. Other theories are associated with attractive forces mediated by electrons transference (electrostatic theory) or by chemisorption due to the formation of van der Waal's, hydrogen and hydrophobic bonding (adsorption theory) and/or fracture strength. Nevertheless, the polymers may be categorized according to the binding type to the mucosa.

Ionic polymers:

The bioadhesive polymers tend to adhere to the biological substrates mostly by interpenetration followed by secondary non-covalent bonding. These secondary interactions are usually hydrogen bonds between the charged polymers' chains with the oligosaccharide side chains of the mucus proteins. Some of the most effective anionic polymers are the polyacrylates (Carbopols) and carboxymethylcelluloses (CMC). The referred mucoadhesive polymers are included in the so-called first-generation and have been intensively used. Their bio adhesion properties come essentially from the H-bonds with their carboxyl functional groups. In addition, the sulfate groups are also characterized by their bio adhesion due to anionic non-covalent and H-bonds. Chitosan is among all cationic polymers one of the most widely used and tested for biomedical and pharmaceutical applications.

Neutral polymers:

Non-ionic polymers can also present bioadhesive properties through non-covalent interactions with the surrounding fluids. For instance, the mucoadhesiveness of PEO and Polycarbophil polymers would be promoted by the high entanglement level of their polymer chains followed by possible hydrogen bonds formation. The concept of chain entanglement emerged early during the nineties in an attempt to explain the mechanical properties of amorphous polymers above the TG. The evidence of its existence is mainly based on the mechanical properties behavior of the materials. Furthermore, despite the physical interlocking of the chains, secondary chemical bonds (as hydrogen bonds) may be formed and would contribute to strengthening the links. Therefore, between the celluloses, the high density of available hydrogen bonding groups may contribute to stronger interactions of the polymer chains with the mucin glycoproteins

Thiomers:

The majority of the polymers referred are essentially water-soluble and their adhesiveness to the mucous membrane arises from their non-covalent bonds after hydration. This property has been widely explored in pharmaceutical technology for several years, but only during the 90s real 'pharmaceutical glue' excipients had been developed. In fact, a clear distinction can be found in literature, a first generation including the mucous non-covalent-bond polymers and a second generation comprising mucous-covalent-bond polymers. These polymers commonly called thiomers are capable of forming covalent bonds, mainly based on thiol /disulfide exchange reactions. The thiol groups of the polymers bond covalently to the cysteine-rich subdomains of the mucus layer by the formation of disulfide bonds. Generally, these second-generation mucoadhesive polymers are usually less sensitive to ionic and pH changes and the disulfide bonds may facilitate controlled drug diffusion due to the higher rigidity and cross-linking. Therefore, these polymers may be preferred to develop modified profile release drug delivery systems whereas the first-generation polymers are preferable to fast onset drug release. Regarding the first generation thiomers, their usage in the development of the oral film may also be challenging due to their inherent instability. Thiomers are unstable in aqueous solutions with $\text{pH} \geq 5$ due to the oxidation of the thiol groups. However, the second generation thiomers are more stable in solutions and in a broader pH range³⁸⁻³⁹.

FUTURE SCOPE OF DEVELOPMENT:

Formulation of a drug into various films has been popular in recent years. Several undesirable drawbacks associated with conventional dosage forms such as inconvenience of administration; lower bioavailability and patient non-compliance have pushed the development of novel polymeric thin films as a drug delivery platform. This drug delivery platform is being under surveillance from both start-up and established pharmaceutical companies. The future looks very promising for the film technology in the time to come as new technologies. Pharmacy preparations such as ODFs create more dose flexibility than a chewable with commercially available products for adults, provide good patient acceptance, and hence increase patient compliance. ODFs can be cut into separate smaller pieces for the adjustment, which is important in pediatrics. ODFs are easy to administer and require almost no intake of water. This makes ODFs a suitable dosage form for patients who have difficulties swallowing large amounts of fluid, are unable to swallow (mini) tablets, are non-cooperative, and are prone to spitting out drugs or suffer from a disease requiring restricted fluid intake, e.g., edema or heart failure. However, the first-pass metabolism can be partly circumvented if absorption via the oral mucosa is promoted. This may improve bioavailability which entails a risk of overdosing if the ODFs are not administered correctly. On the other hand, an improved bioavailability may reduce the dose needed and contribute to a reduction of side effects. ODFs are also convenient portable dosage forms. This is an advantage compared to brittle and fragile orodispersible tablets and liquid dosage forms that demand a special package for transportation or are only available in large bottles. Up to now, there are no standard formulations for the preparation of ODFs available in the Dutch or in any other national formulary. However, research in this field is ongoing and promising⁴⁰⁻⁴¹.

CONCLUSION

Fast dissolving oral films have several advantages over the conventional dosage forms. Fast dissolving oral film is most acceptable and accurate oral dosage form which bypasses the hepatic system and therapeutic response. The unique properties of films are easy administration, fast disintegration, consumer preference, rapid action, etc making it as a useful delivery form of medication intended for geriatric, pediatrics or dysphasic patients who have difficulty in swallowing tablets and capsule. The companies prefer this dosage form due to both patient compliance (especially pediatric and geriatric) as well as industrial acceptability.

REFERENCE

1. Castán H, Ruiz MA, Clares B, Morales ME. Design, development, and characterization of buccal bioadhesive films of Doxepin for treatment of odontalgia. *Drug Deliv.* 2015;22(6):869–76.
2. Costa IDM, Abranches RP, Garcia MTJ, Pierre MBR. Chitosan-based mucoadhesive films containing 5-aminolevulinic acid for buccal cancer's treatment. *J Photochem Photobiol B.* 2014;140:266–75.
3. Morales JO, McConville JT. Novel strategies for the buccal delivery of macromolecules. *Drug Dev Ind Pharm.* 2014;40:579–90.
4. Castro PM, Fonte P, Sousa F, Madureira AR, Sarmento B, Pintado ME. Oral films as breakthrough tools for oral delivery of proteins/peptides. *J Control Release.* 2015;211:63–73.
5. China M. Overview of biological products. Center for Drug Evaluation and Research U.S. Food and Drug Administration FDA Webinar; 2013.
6. Zhao L, Ren T, Wang DD. Clinical pharmacology considerations in biologics development. *Acta Pharmacol Sin.* 2012;33:1339–47.
7. Abruzzo A, Bigucci F, Cerchiara T, Cruciani F, Vitali B, Luppi B. Mucoadhesive chitosan/gelatin films for buccal delivery of propranolol hydrochloride. *Carbohydr Polym.* 2012; 87:581–85.
8. Senel S, Kremer M, Nagy K, Squier C. Delivery of bioactive peptides and proteins across oral (buccal) mucosa. *Curr Pharm Biotechnol.* 2001;2:175–86.
9. Maniruzzaman M, Boateng JS, Snowden MJ, et al. A review of hot-melt extrusion: process technology for pharmaceutical products. *ISRN Pharm* 2012;2012:1–9.
10. Patel VF, Liu F, Brown MB. Advances in oral transmucosal drug delivery. *J Control Release* 2011;153:106–116.
11. Borges AF, Silva C, Coelho JF, et al. Oral films: current status and future perspectives: I - Galenical development and quality attributes. *J Control Release* 2015;206:1–19.
12. Sharma D, Kaur D, Verma S, et al. Fast dissolving oral films technology: a recent trend for an innovative oral drug delivery system. *Int J Drug Deliv* 2015;7:60–75.
13. Kang-Miller JJ, Osswald CR, Mieler WF. Advances in ocular drug delivery: emphasis on the posterior segment. *Expert Opin Drug Deliv* 2014;11:1–14.
14. Castro PM, Fonte P, Sousa F, et al. Oral films as breakthrough tools for oral delivery of proteins/peptides. *J Control Release* 2015;211:63–73.
15. Barbu E, Verestiuc L, Nevell TG, et al. Polymeric materials for ophthalmic drug delivery: trends and perspectives. *J Mater Chem* 2006;16:3439–3443.
16. Achouri D, Alhanout K, Piccerelle P, et al. Recent advances in ocular drug delivery. *Drug Dev Ind Pharm* 2013;39:1599–1671.
17. Walsch J, Cram A, Woertz K, Breikreutz J, Winzenburg G, Turner R, et al. Playing hide and seek with poorly tasting pediatric medicines: do not forget the excipients. *Adv Drug Deliv.* 2014;73:14–23.
18. Preis M. Orally disintegrating films and mini-tablets—innovative dosage forms of choice for pediatric use. *AAPS PharmSciTech.* 2015;16(2):234–41.
19. Ivanovska V, Rademaker CMA, van Dijk L, Mantel-Teeuwisse A. Pediatric drug formulations: a review of challenges and progress. *Pediatrics* 2014;134(2):361–72.
20. Standing JF, Tuleu C. Paediatric formulations—getting to the heart of the problem. *Int J Pharm.* 2005;300:56–66.
21. 't Jong GW, Vulto AG, de Hoog M, Schimmel KJM, Tibboel D, van den Anker JN. A survey of the use of off-label and unlicensed drugs in a Dutch children's hospital. *Pediatrics.* 2001;108(5):1089–93.
22. Strickley RG, Iwata Q, Wu S, Dahl TC. Pediatric drugs—a review of commercially available oral formulations. *J Pharm Sci.* 2008;97(5):1731–74.
23. Turner MA, Catapano M, Giaquinto C, On behalf of GRIP (Global Research in Paediatrics). Pediatric drug development: the impact of evolving regulations. *Adv Drug Deliv Rev.* 2014;736:2–13.
24. Nahata MC, Allen Jr LV. Extemporaneous drug formulations. *Clin Ther.* 2008;30(11):2112–9.
25. Florence AT, Attwood D. Physicochemical principles of pharmacy. In: *Manufacture, formulation and clinical use. Pediatric and geriatric formulations.* London: Pharmaceutical Press; 2016. p. 427–41.
26. Sastry SV, Nyshadham JR, Fix JA. Recent technological advances in oral drug delivery e a review. *Pharm Sci Technol* 2000;3:138-145.
27. Sapna K, Sharma V, Singh L. Fast disintegrating tablet: a boon to pediatric and geriatric. *Int J Pharma Professional's Res* 2011;2:18-326.
28. Haywood A, Glass BD. Liquid dosage forms extemporaneously prepared from commercially available products e considering new evidence on stability. *J Pharm Pharm Sci* 2013;16:441-455.
29. Wu J, Yang C, Rong Y, et al. Preparation and nutritional characterization of perilla chewable tablet. *Procedia Eng* 2012;37:202-207.
30. Suzuki H, Onishi H, Takahashi Y, et al. Development of oral acetaminophen chewable tablets with inhibited bitter taste. *Int J Pharm* 2003;251:123-132.
31. Mullarney MP, Hancock BC, Carlson GT, et al. The powder flow and compact mechanical properties of sucrose and three high-intensity sweeteners used in chewable tablets. *Int J Pharm* 2003;257:227-236.
32. Stephan D, Honerlagen H, Mitschka J, et al. Effervescent tablet. U.S. Patent application 005171571, December 1992.
33. Dey P, Maiti S. Orodispersible tablets: a new trend in drug delivery. *J Nat Sci Biol Med* 2010;1:2

34. Kulkarni U, Basawaraj P, Hari Prasanna C, Prashant B, Hogade M G, Rabbani G, Formulation and Development of Fast Dissolving Meloxicam Tablets by Solid dispersion Technique for effective Treatment of Dental pain. Int J o Current Pharma Research, 2010, 2(3), 82-85.
35. Arya A, Chandra A, Sharma V, Pathak K, Fast Dissolving Oral Films: An Innovative Drug Delivery System and Dosage Form. Int J of ChemTech Research, 2010, 2(1), 576- 583.
36. Mahajan A, Chhabra N, Aggarwal G, Formulation and Characterization of Fast Dissolving Buccal Films: A Review, Scholars Research Library, 2011, 3(1), 152-165.
37. Corniello CM, Quick-Dissolve Strips: From Concept to Commercialization. Drug Delivery. Tech., 2006, 6(2),68-71
38. Fankhauser C, Slominski G, Meyer S, Disintegrable Oral Films, U.S. Patent 0202057, Aug. 30, 2007.
39. Kulkarni N, Kumar LD, Sorg A, Fast dissolving Orally Consumable Films containing An Antitussive and A mucosa coating agent, U.S. Patent 206942, Nov 6, 2003.
40. Dixit RP, Puthli SP, Oral Strip Technology: Overview and future potential. J. Controlled. Release, 2009, 139, 94-107.
41. Leduy A, Zajic JE, Luong JHT, Pullulan In Encyclopedia of Polymer Science and Engineering, 2nd ed., Wiley & Sons, New York, 1988, 650.

Submit your next manuscript to **IAJPR** and take advantage of:

- Convenient online manuscript submission
- Access Online first
- Double blind peer review policy
- International recognition
- No space constraints or color figure charges
- Immediate publication on acceptance
- Inclusion in **ScopeMed** and other full-text repositories
- Redistributing your research freely

Submit your manuscript at: editorinchief@iajpr.com

